

SIMULATIONS OF THERMOMECHANICAL PERFORMANCE OF SMP-BASED MICROVASCULAR SYSTEMS

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1. Introduction

Shape memory polymers[1] is a new class of active materials that have potential for applications such as biomedical devices, surface patterning, and light weight morphing structures. Recently, microvascular systems were proposed and developed by one of the authors' group[2] and have demonstrated improved thermal management and shape recovery performance. This paper further investigates the performance of this microvascular system through simulation-based parametric design studies. Design guidelines of such systems are then discussed.

2. Microvascular System and Experiments

Details about fabrication of microvascular system can be found in Phillips and Baur[2]. Briefly, the SMP used for this work was Veriflex (Cornerstone Research Group, Dayton, OH). Ten stainless steel tubes of 203 μ m OD, 102 μ m ID, and 489mm long were used as the vascular tubes. The SMP resin was filled into a model then annealed. The final panel measured 146mm parallel to the tubes, 170mm perpendicular to the tubes, and 1.69mm thick. A mechanical recovery experiment was run for the panel with microvascular heating. After programming a shape of 20% strain (in the direction perpendicular to the tube direction), one edge of the panel was released from the fixture. The heating protocol was 25ml/min of water delivered at 110°C.

3 Models

3.1 Material Model for SMP

A multi-branch thermoviscoelastic constitutive model was used to capture the shape memory behavior of the SMP used. More details about the model can be found in [3][4]. Parameter identification was conducted by fitting the DMA $\tan\delta$ curve, shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Parameter fitting using the DMA test.

Fig. 2. Modeling method in ABAQUS in the 2D setting. (a) Dimension illustration of a representative microvascular SMP composite. (b) Finite element mesh for the half-size periodic unit cell.

3.2 FEA Model for Microvascular System

FEA software ABAQUS was used. Fig. 2 shows the FEA model of the representative case, whose dimensions matched those in the experiment. Due to symmetry, only a half of the periodic model was analyzed. For thermal boundary conditions, the top

surface was applied with “surface radiation” condition with the ambient temperature of 25°C. Other surfaces were applied with insulate condition. In a SM cycle, the model was first stretched by 20% at 110°C. After the shape was fixed, hot water was delivered at 110°C (25ml/min) to activate the SMP composite for free shape recovery.

Fig. 3 The comparison between the simulation and experiments. The shape recovery ratio is captured on Point 3 in the stretching direction.

4. Results

4.1 Comparison with experiments

Fig. 3 shows the simulated recovery behavior of the microvascular system, as well as the temperature evolution on Point 1 and Point 3 (shown in Fig. 2) and the comparison with the experiment. It is seen that the FEA simulation matched experiment very well. Fig. 4 shows the temperature distribution within the half-size periodic model during the SM cycle. It can be seen that the free shape recovery behavior of the SMP composite is a process coupled by the thermal conduction and thermally induced shape recovery. Point 1 recovers faster than point 3 because it has higher temperature.

4.2 Parametric studies

Fig. 5 shows a representative parametric study where the composite is heated by the water of temperatures of 90 °C, 100 °C, 110 °C and 120°C, respectively. It is clear that the higher the water temperature the faster the recovery rate.

5. Conclusions

Finite element studies were carried out to study the performance of a SMP based microvascular system for the improved thermal management and shape

recovery. Comparison between model simulation and experiment shows very good agreements. Parametric studies revealed design guidelines of such systems.

Fig. 4 Temperature distribution within the half-size periodic unit cell during the finite element analysis.

Fig. 5. Shape recovery ratio of the SMP composite under different heating conditions where the composite is heated by the water temperature at 90 °C, 100 °C, 110 °C and 120°C, respectively.

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